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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D1.4) presents an operational framework to assess resilience (Operational Resilience Framework, ORF) in forest social-ecological systems. The framework is based on a series of elements: system variables (forest ecosystem services and elements of the forest value chain), disturbances and stressors acting at certain spatiotemporal scales, reference state whose characteristics are intended to be maintained, and metrics to compare the observed values of the system variables to the reference state. These elements fit into a logical narrative that allows the identification of predictors and co-drivers that reflect the mechanisms determining the resilience of system variables. This approximation has a deterministic basis, but its flexibility allows a broad application.

Keywords

Common Framework, Resilience approach, Operational, Resistance, Recovery, Stability, Vulnerability, Forest social-ecological resilience.

1 Introduction

This deliverable (D1.4) presents an Operational Resilience Framework based on the previous work carried out from the literature review in [deliverable 1.1](#) (D1.1) and [deliverable 1.2](#) (D1.2). This framework has been developed to assess the resilience of forest social-ecological systems, in order to offer a common scheme for RESONATE tasks and also with the aim to be further applied beyond RESONATE project in future projects dealing with forest resilience.

1.1 The concept of resilience

The **concept of resilience** has been used in multiple disciplines (environmental sciences, ecology, economics, sociology, psychology) (Folke 2006; Biggs 2015, Hallegatte et al. 2016; Moser et al. 2019) in which it has acquired different meanings. In ecology, it is defined as the ability of a system to maintain its properties in the face of environmental variability, without surpassing a threshold that implies a shift to an alternative stable state (named **ecological resilience**) (Holling 1973, Scheffer et al. 2015). This environmental variability may be associated with disturbances that cause sudden loss of organisms or biomass; in this situation, resilience corresponds to the system's ability to recover the properties altered by the disturbance (named **engineering resilience** or elasticity) (DeAngelis 1980, Holling 1996). In addition, the concept of resilience is applied to social-ecological systems, which include natural and social components; in this case, resilience can be defined as the system's capacity to reorganize in response to unexpected shocks or under gradual changes and adapt through multi-scale interactions between social and ecological system components (named **social-ecological resilience**) (Biggs 2015). Under this perspective, ecosystem services play an integrative role by coupling ecosystem functioning to the demands of human societies. Also, socioeconomic resilience (Hallegatte et al. 2016) broadly agrees with this approach since it refers to the capacity to maintain assets and welfare in front of unexpected shocks. This concept of social-ecological resilience is consistent with the definition of resilience adopted by the UN as "*the ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate to and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions*" (UNISDR, WMO 2012).

Ecological, engineering, and social-ecological resilience approaches appear nested through a hierarchical relationship, also reflecting the complexity of the systems and the environmental variability (Nikinmaa et al. 2020). In fact, these three different approaches to resilience can be summarized under a common description: "*capacity of a system to absorb a disturbance or an environmental transformation, and reorganize while undergoing change, retaining essentially the same structure, identity, and feedbacks*" (Folke et al. 2004; Walker et al. 2004). In this description, different **essential elements** can be recognized: (i) a system characterized by a set of variables (**system variables**), (ii) a transformation of the environment (**stress or disturbance**), and (iii) the maintenance of the system's characteristics (**a reference state**).

The generality of the concept of resilience and its application in multiple contexts has expanded its widespread use and has been adopted by political agendas, decision-making agents, and environmental managers (Benson and Garmenstani 2011), especially in a context in which adaptation to climate change is gaining priority. Resilience to climate change, however, often presents important vagueness for its analysis and implementation, since the characteristics of the system that are intended to be maintained and the drivers associated

with climate change (i.e., increase in temperature, extreme weather events, disturbance regime) frequently are not specifically addressed.

1.2 The need for a common framework

In recent years, many proposals have emerged to build conceptual frameworks for resilience based on different criteria, such as the scope of application (Garmestani and Benson 2013; Haider et al 2021), the relationship with other conceptual frameworks - such as vulnerability (Miller et al. 2010), stability (Donohue et al 2016; Hillebrand et al. 2018; de Bello et al 2021), adaptability and transformability (Folke et al. 2010) or sustainability (Redman 2014) -, its relation to the disturbance regime (Johnstone et al. 2016), the involved mechanisms (Falk et al. 2022), or the way to measure it (Ingrish and Bahn 2018; Bryant et al 2019; Chuang et al. 2019). These proposals are sometimes focused on specific systems, such as forests (DeRose and Long 2016; Johnstone et al. 2016; Bryant et al 2019; Albrich et al. 2020; Nikinmaa et al. 2020; Falk et al. 2022). Although some procedures to assess and apply the resilience concept have been proposed (Standish et al. 2014; Baho et al. 2017; Chambers et al. 2020; Tamberg et al. 2021), their implementation, in terms of application of measures to promote resilience, usually is not fully developed. Indeed, there is still a lack of an operational standardization of the use of resilience. That is, common, consistent, and unambiguous terminology, and a basic procedure to measure resilience across the vast range of domains in which it is used from ecological to socio-economic systems. Thus, we need an operative framework integrating theoretical developments, empirical knowledge, and social agents and decision-makers for the implementation of measures that would increase the resilience of forest social-ecological systems (Donohue et al. 2016; Nikinmaa et al. 2020; Nikinmaa et al. 2023).

In this deliverable, we present an **operational framework to assess resilience** (Operational Resilience Framework, ORF), suitable to be applied in different domains, from natural to social sciences, and particularly in social-ecological systems. The ORF consists of (i) a **glossary** of terms that identify the basic elements necessary to understand resilience, thus providing a unified terminology applicable to different contexts, (ii) the **relationships** between these elements, and (iii) a **sequence of steps** for assessing resilience in a given system. In our context, operational implies that the proposed framework to assess resilience in a specific situation (specific resilience *sensu* Folke et al. 2010) should be:

- 1) able to compare resilience among different contexts (e.g., regions, regulations, management practices, type or magnitude of disturbance/stress). Therefore, a quantitative approach based on resilience measuring is preferable.
- 2) suitable to:
 - supply information on current and future forest system resilience.
 - establish targets for action plans,
 - monitor the effects of policy implementation,
 - predict statistically and mechanistically resilience by analysing the performance of system variables in response to disturbances or stress,
 - support the identification of key factors that challenge or promote resilience.

The validity of the developed framework is supported by an intensive literature review of resilience in forests, including their ecological functioning and their related value chains (see [D1.1](#) and [D1.2](#)). This search allows us to verify the viability of the proposed framework in a multitude of studies with different perspectives, objectives, and measures of resilience.

2 The Operational Resilience Framework

2.1 Basic principles

The ORF is based on several **basic principles**:

- The forest social-ecological system is described by a set of **system variables** (i.e., variables related to the forest ecosystem services or the forest value chain), which are measurable, preferably quantitatively.
- Resilience is here assumed as “**resilience of what to what**” (Carpenter et al. 2001), i.e., it refers to the system variable’s (of what) performance through time in response to particular disturbances or stressors (to what).
- Resilience of a system affected by disturbance(s) or stressor(s) is quantitatively compared to a **reference state**.

The logical structure of the ORF (see Fig. 1) is based on the fact that the system variables that define a social-ecological system are modified by disturbances or stressors. Resilience can then be estimated by comparing these modified system variables to reference values corresponding to the absence of disturbance or stress, or to situations in which the variables remain within margins that are considered adequate (i.e., reference state). The closer the variables of the system affected by disturbances or stressors reach these reference values, the greater the resilience. Since this resilience obeys certain mechanisms that operate in the system, it is possible to find explanatory variables that reflect these mechanisms (i.e., resilience predictors). Thus, a change in the values of these variables indicates that the resilience of the system tends to increase or decrease. Some of these variables are susceptible to manipulation and therefore may be useful in determining actions that can be taken to promote resilience (i.e., resilience predictors). Other factors describe context situations that are difficult to manipulate (i.e., co-drivers), but that are important to consider, in order to identify the potential for resilience in that context. By applying this procedure, ORF provides a common rationale to different cases, allowing for comparisons, and a formal consistency for resilience assessment.

Figure 1. Graphical abstract summarizing the main concepts of the Operational Resilience Framework (ORF). Tree icons made by Gabriela Rueda.

2.2 Elements of the ORF

The operational resilience framework is based on 8 main elements defined as follows:

2.2.1 Resilience approach:

We identify three major approaches to resilience, according to the literature, as described above: engineering, ecological and social-ecological resilience.

It is important to recognize which approach will be used when assessing resilience in specific situations (e.g., empirical case studies, literature sources). The approach will help to identify other elements of the ORF, such as the type of system variables (i.e., corresponding to the forest social-ecological system), the existence of disturbances or stressors, the selected reference state (i.e., an undisturbed situation or a range of values describing a dynamic equilibrium), or to determine the metric selected for comparing the observed state of the variables to a reference state. Some simple rules indicate that:

- **engineering resilience** applies if the assessment corresponds to disturbances that interrupt the historical range of environmental variation,
- **ecological resilience** applies if the assessment involves variability of system variables which eventually may result in ecological thresholds and state shifts related to changing environmental or socio-economic conditions,
- **social-ecological resilience** applies if the assessment explicitly refers to the maintenance or improvement of social or economic parameters.

2.2.2 System variables: Resilience OF what?

System variables are quantitative parameters describing characteristics of the social-ecological system that respond to disturbances, stressors, and other co-drivers. These variables correspond to stocks or flows of energy, matter, or information, and can operate at different scales, from the tree (e.g., annual growth) and the plot (e.g., biomass), to the landscape (e.g., forest cover) and the whole country or state (e.g., harvested timber). It is important to highlight that the system variables correspond to the system properties of interest whose resilience is going to be analysed, that is, their ability to recover or maintain under the effects of disturbances or stressors. Therefore, they correspond to "**of What**" following the "Resilience of What to What" approach (Carpenter et al. 2001) ("responses" *sensu* Albrich et al. 2020).

In the context of aiming to integrate the forest ecosystem with social benefits, system variables often correspond to ecosystem services or value chain components (see [D1.1](#), Hurtado et al. 2022, and [D1.2](#), Jaime et al. 2023 for literature reviews of the system variables used in studies of resilience in forest social-ecological systems). The use of ecosystem services as system variables is particularly useful since it allows connecting the ecological functioning of forests with the sustainability of the associated socio-economic subsystem. In brief, the analysis and management of the resilience of the ecosystem services of provision, support, regulation, and culture, is especially appropriate when it comes to evaluating social-ecological systems (Lecina-Díaz et al. 2020).

In general, system variables can be identified in indicator lists such as MAES ecosystem service indicators or UNECE compilations (Maes et al. 2016; UNECE 2021). However, notice that when referring to the resilience of forest social-ecological systems, the term "indicators" is used in literature and assessments in two different ways: (1) descriptors of the properties of the system that is experiencing resilience (e.g., the resilience of carbon storage under climate change can be estimated by the performance of the indicator "forest stand biomass"), and (2) predictors of the resilience of given properties of the system (e.g., higher "stand tree diversity" can be an indicator of higher resilience of timber production under climate change); so, if they are modified, resilience will respond by increasing or diminishing. Our framework explicitly distinguishes these two meanings as "system variables" and "resilience predictors" (see

below), respectively. Note that some system variables commonly act as predictors of the resilience of other system variables. This is consistent with our operational approach, which starts by identifying those system variables that are relevant for the analysis and promotion of resilience, and then, searches for reliable predictors of that resilience.

Even recognizing the complexity of the system, with multiple feedbacks, it is convenient to select a limited number of system variables that define the functionality of the system. Many system variables are associated due to causal relationships between them, or because they are generated from common processes. For example, numerous variables may describe the degree of forest productivity or economic growth, and their resilience may show common patterns. But these system variables may represent complementary aspects of the behaviour of the system. They may correspond to different subsystems, such as the ecological or the social ones, and may even represent conflicting interests, which must be balanced (here the concept of trade-offs applies). For this reason, it is usually convenient to jointly analyse the resilience of different system variables. For this, we can use multivariate approaches that describe the trajectory of the system in the face of disturbances or stressors across the space defined by different variables (Seidl et al. 2014), multi-criteria analysis (de Bremond and Engle 2014), or optimization models that contemplate the resilience of different system variables (Pohjanmies et al. 2021).

2.2.3 Reference state: Resilience COMPARED to what?

The reference state corresponds to a scenario that serves as a basis for comparison with the system state after disturbance or under stress. In other words, it is the measure of the state of the system variables to which the observations of the response to disturbances or stresses are confronted. The reference state is a fundamental piece of the ORF. Without it, a description of the system's behaviour in the face of disturbances or stress can be provided, but we are not properly considering resilience. In fact, this reference state makes it possible to operationalize the idea of "maintaining the properties and functionalities of the system", as resilience is defined. However, the reference state is not an absolute value of the system, because different reference states may exist, according to the definition of the undisturbed or the desired state. Therefore, when analysing resilience under different scenarios (e.g., climate change or management), a specific scenario, often corresponding to a baseline situation, needs to be established as the reference state (Grimm and Wissel 1997).

If we adopt an engineering resilience perspective, in which resilience is associated with disturbances, the reference state corresponds to the undisturbed system. In a situation that assumes a steady state with no historical legacies or high recovery rates, the reference state may correspond to the pre-disturbance situation, as is often used in many studies. However, in historical systems, such as those affected by climate change or social and economic transformations, the past context cannot be maintained, and the comparison with the system before being disturbed loses meaning. In such cases, comparison with a contemporary undisturbed reference system may be more appropriate, at the cost of incorporating spatial variability into the analysis.

If an ecological resilience approach is adopted, the reference state corresponds to the range of values of the system variables that define the size of the basin of attraction (Scheffer et al. 2001) in which a dynamic equilibrium is established, different from other alternative states. When the variables of the observed system move away from such values and go near an ecological threshold, resilience diminishes. So, the higher variability of system variables, the higher likelihood to escape from the basin of attraction and reaching a threshold leading to an alternative state, thus, indicating lower resilience.

In studies addressing social-ecological resilience, disturbances are often not explicitly defined and the system follows an irreversible time path constrained by secular stressors (social changes, climate change), punctuated by crises. In this case, the degree of functionality of the system corresponds to collective decisions, including actions from political and economic agents that determine how they aim for the system to work, for example, maintaining or increasing the well-being of people, production of goods, economic activity or conservation of natural processes and biodiversity. From a social-ecological perspective, a certain level of ecosystem services is a good candidate to become the reference state. Here, the desired trends, which are the object of management, constitute the reference system, which for operational purposes, is translated into certain rates of change - either zero, positive or negative. In this case, the establishment of the reference state suffers from greater arbitrariness and therefore requires an adequate justification, which does not usually occur in most of the literature.

A related case is socio-economic resilience in the face of natural disasters, which has been defined as "the ability of an economy to minimize the impact of asset losses on wellbeing" due to natural hazards (Hallegate et al. 2016), following the UNISDR definition of resilience as "*the ability to resist, absorb, accommodate and recover in a timely and efficient manner*" (UNISDR, WMO 2012). Here the system variables are the measures of assets and wellbeing, while the reference state corresponds to the minimum loss of wellbeing given a certain loss of assets caused by a natural hazard. Accordingly, this resilience has been proposed to be estimated as the respective asset losses relative to wellbeing losses as a consequence of natural disasters (Hallegate et al. 2016). Note that here there is no direct comparison with an undamaged, reference system, instead, the reference state corresponds to a loss of wellbeing equivalent to the asset loss.

2.2.4 Disturbance/stressor: Resilience TO what?

There are relevant environmental or social-economical changes affecting the social-ecological system. These changes can be episodic (i.e., disturbances), gradual, or chronic (i.e., stress), and in all cases, they disrupt the historical, regular functioning of the system. See [D1.2](#) (Jaime et al. 2023) for the main disturbances addressed in studies on resilience in forest social-ecological systems, where resilience predictors were found. In the absence of such disturbances or stress, resilience does not actually occur and cannot be measured properly. However, during periods without disturbance or heavy stress, the system may acquire features that will improve its resilience in front of future disturbance or stress. For instance, an extensive and long-term institutional and legislative adaptation to forest multifunctional management may favour the resilience of the whole forest socio-ecological system to oncoming shock-causing bark-beetle outbreaks (Hlásny et al. 2021), but such adaptation measures must be developed in advance to the outbreak.

The existence of disturbances or stressors helps to guide the selection of the resilience approach to be used in the assessment (see above). However, the distinction between disturbances and stressors is not always clear. Indeed, several types of disturbances have been recognized, from discrete, episodic pulses to press and ramp disturbances, and even small stochastic disturbances, (Lake 2000; Van Meerbeek et al. 2021) which would converge with the idea of stress (Grime 1974). Statistical criteria have been proposed to recognize extreme events and trends in relation to the historical series of the variability of environmental parameters, such as climate (Katz et al. 2005). These extremes can constitute disturbances when they involve the loss of stocks, such as biomass, accompanied by rapid changes in flows, which may be transitory. The set of characteristics of intensity, distribution in space, and sequence in time of the set of disturbances experienced by a system constitute its disturbance

regime. Importantly, since the disturbance regime operates through time in a given territory, it must be referred to in specific spatio-temporal scales, as described for resilience. In turn, stress does not usually have a clear episodic character like pulse disturbances, although it can exhibit clear tendencies, associated with important variability, in space and time. Disturbances and stressors do not usually occur in isolation, instead different disturbance events together with stressors may affect the same social-ecological system. Thus, resilience assessment would refer to compound disturbances which may include several disturbance and stressor types (Johnstone et al. 2016).

Climate change is a situation in which there is a combination of stress and disturbances owing to (i) a warming trend that can increase stress, in particular when combined with a decrease in precipitation, (ii) an increase in climate variability that leads to extreme episodes (e.g., heat waves, droughts, hurricanes), (iii) a boosting of other disturbances (e.g., wildfires, outbreaks) or stressors (e.g., socio-economic changes). Therefore, the resilience to climate change of forest social-ecological systems must consider this entire set of drivers.

2.2.5 Spatio-temporal scale: **WHEN** and **WHERE** is resilience operating?

Resilience is a temporal concept, which refers to specific temporal scales and periods which should be explicitly defined when assessing resilience (Standish et al. 2014). Disturbances, social shocks, environmental transformations, and their consequence on ecosystems (recovery, state shifts, reorganization, and adaptation) occur at given times across a specific temporal frame. Also, importantly, regulatory feedbacks of the system do not operate instantaneously and delays in the responses to disturbance and stress are the rule. So, resilience must be explicitly referred to in the time extent at which recovery from disturbances or response to stressors occurs. For example, a system may be erroneously considered low-resilient because it has been given little time to recover after a disturbance, or high-resilient because the stress experienced has been of short duration.

The temporal scale is tightly linked to the spatial one. Social-ecological systems are located in territories, which determine the extent of stocks and fluxes, as well as the regulatory and social context. Disturbance regimes are by definition framed within time and space, and stress impact is also strongly dependent on its duration. Importantly, key mechanisms determining resilience often change across such spatiotemporal contexts, and they are strongly linked to the spatiotemporal distribution of disturbances and stress (Jentsch and White 2019), as reflected, for instance, by cumulative effects (Johnstone et al 2016). So, the responses of the forest social-ecological system to disturbances and stress and the responsible mechanisms should also be interpreted in the same spatiotemporal context. In turn, the spatial scale is often strongly related to the levels of organization involved in decision-making, from local owners to municipalities and states and countries, which also correspond to the temporal scale at which a system's resilience-derived responses emerge and should be assessed.

As a general rule, resilience should be analysed considering larger spatio-temporal scales than the one just covering the appearance of single disturbances or stress. From an ecological resilience perspective, a system may appear very resilient because it remains in a given state over time, until the cumulative effects of stress, sometimes accompanied by disturbances, reach an ecological threshold that leads to a change in the ecosystem state. Alternatively, mechanisms that promote resilience, such as the accumulation of stocks or the generation of trade networks or information flows, often operate before a shock occurs. Therefore, from the operational point of view that seeks to promote resilience before the occurrence of disturbance or stressors, the effects of these mechanisms must be extrapolated to situations that have not yet appeared, including disturbances with high intensity. For instance, a certain forest stand may be resilient to storms up to a certain wind speed, probably corresponding to the past

storm regime, but it is seldom resilient to hurricanes, which are likely to appear in a future climate. In other words, a decoupling between the generation of the mechanisms that increase or reduce resilience and the moment of impact or recovery is common. This forces us to consider broad spatio-temporal scales, as well as intensities and frequencies of disturbances and stressors that may not correspond to historical regimes.

Finally, it is important to highlight that the spatio-temporal scale is a transversal element across the ORF, also framing other elements, including disturbances and stress.

2.2.6 Resilience metric: HOW is resilience quantified?

Resilience metrics imply quantitative methods to measure the performance of system variable(s) of a given forest social-ecological system in response to disturbances or stressors. Importantly, this measurement implies some kind of comparison between the observed system variable(s) after disturbance or under stress and a given reference state. The selected metric must allow for assessing the effect of resilience predictors and, ideally, the intensity of their effect on different situations, which will correspond to co-drivers (see below) such as climate, management legacies, or region. So, in principle, it should be distinguished between the specific metric used to quantify resilience, and the analytical method employed to assess the effect of potential statistical explanatory variables on this metric. In some cases, however, this distinction may be obscured because the way to quantify resilience is through the analytical method itself, for instance when using models to test for significant differences between disturbed or stressed systems and the reference state. In fact, the estimation of the resilience may be strongly dependent on the metric used, since different methodologies emphasize different components of resilience (e.g., resistance or recovery) (e.g., Zheng et al. 2021), but they also reflect the relationship between different system variables or the temporal scale. This represents an important challenge to compare different situations, although some techniques of meta-analysis may support overall assessments (Ibañez et al. 2019).

There are many different quantitative methods to measure resilience - according to the resilience approach -, the occurrence of disturbances or stressors, the number and attributes of the system variables, and the features of the reference state. In addition, resilience measures may vary according to the specific features of the system considered (e.g., its biogeographic or political context), the assessment goals, and the available information. Therefore, several criteria can be applied to select the specific procedures for measuring resilience in each case: (i) focus of the analysis on disturbances (engineering resilience approach), variability around a dynamic equilibrium or ecological thresholds leading to alternative states (ecological resilience approach), (ii) single or multiple system variables, (iii) temporal recording of system variables providing discrete or continuous sets of data, (iv) acquisition of data following a diachronic or synchronic procedure, in relation to disturbances or events. Examples of resilience measuring include indices based on comparison to undisturbed systems (Lloret et al 2011, Hillebrand et al 2018), recovery parameters - such as recovery rate (Meng et al 2020), time to full recovery (Thum et al. 2016) or recovery to resistance biplot analysis (Ingrisch and Bahn 2018) - significant differences in statistical models (e.g., Waltz et al. 2014), multivariate trajectories and distances in relation to a reference state (Sánchez-Pinillos et al. 2019; Sommerfeld et al. 2020), equilibrium analysis based on system maintenance maintain within a given state (Hirota et al 2011), variability estimations (e.g., Pappas et al. 2020; Jourdan et al 2022), early warning signals or critical slowing down (Cailleret et al 2019; Forzieri et al. 2022) and time-series analysis of system variables (Gazol et al. 2016). See [D1.2](#) (Jaime et al. 2023) for a literature review of the metrics and methodological procedures carried out in studies of resilience in forest social-ecological systems.

2.2.7 Resilience predictors: Do parameters that **PREDICT** resilience and that can be **MODIFIED/MANAGED** exist?

Resilience predictors are variables that allow the estimation of the resilience of the system and can be modified through management. For instance, higher tree functional diversity may lead to higher resilience of primary production in the face of drought and other disturbances (Sousa-Silva et al. 2018; Grossiord 2019; Messier et al. 2022). Thus, resilience predictors are a key concept within the ORF, since they provide estimations of prospective resilience (i.e., estimate the capacity to absorb disturbances that have not yet occurred or stress that has not yet deeply modified the system). Importantly, they also address the operational need to plan and develop actions to promote resilience. Note that although resilience cannot be measured properly in the absence of disturbances or stress, resilience predictors inform on how prone a system is to be resilient when these environmental changes will eventually occur. That is, they inform and indicate if a system is becoming more or less resilient and, in addition, these predictors can become a target of management to promote resilience.

Therefore, a link is established between the resilience predictors and the system variables for which resilience is predicted. See [D1.1](#) (Hurtado et al. 2022) for a literature review of the resilience predictors reported in studies of resilience in forest social-ecological systems, and [D1.2](#) (Jaime et al. 2023) for their link with system variables. When models are applied in the analysis of resilience, the predictors can correspond to inputs of the model that determine the output of the variables of the system. Also, sometimes the predictors correspond to scenarios that result in different outputs. For example, different scenarios of management at stand-level may act as predictors since they result in different levels of basal area or tree size structure. However, in many studies that follow a social-ecological approach, resilience predictors are not explicitly quantified, instead, they are narratively justified. In these cases, categorical predictors (e.g., managed vs no managed forests) can be used, although the more accurate and precise the predictor estimates, the more reliable the resilience assessment will be.

Importantly, resilience predictors are scale-dependent. They may cease to be manageable at certain scales and in that case, they should be considered as co-drivers (see below). For example, the taxonomic identity of trees can be a good predictor of the resilience of primary production at the plot level and can be managed in favour of certain species. However, at the regional level, this taxonomic identity appears constrained by biogeographical patterns and biomes and become difficult to manipulate, thus turning into a co-driver in our framework.

Since we assume some level of causality in the relationship between resilience predictors and system variables, this relationship reflects the underlying mechanisms of the system functioning. This recognition of mechanisms promoting resilience is essential for several reasons. First, to avoid spurious relationships which can lead to undesired collateral effects when implementing predictors in management or decision-making. Second, it allows extrapolating the analysis of resilience and its implementation to situations other than those initially analysed, by interpreting the mechanisms in different contexts. For example, functional diversity in forests can promote the resilience of primary production through functional complementarity (i.e., resource partitioning) which is particularly important in fluctuating environments and can be favoured by broadening the range of functional traits (del Rio et al. 2022). Alternatively, functional diversity may be more decisive for resilience in the face of some types of stress, such as drought, by the selection of species with certain traits (Loreau and Hector 2001; Grossiord 2019).

Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain resilience, which show a more comprehensive meaning when viewed from a system dynamics perspective, including stocks, fluxes, feedbacks, and interaction networks between system elements. Overall, systems with

multiple regulatory feedbacks tend to be more resilient than simple, impoverished ones (Meadows and Wright 2008): stored stocks, resource pluses released by disturbances (Jentsch and White 2019), efficiency in the use of resources (Ivanov and Dolgui 2019), processes that reduce lag responses after disturbances (Oliver et al. 2015; Grossiord 2019), redundancy (Standish et al. 2014), connectivity, and adaption capacity (Folke et al. 2010).

2.2.8 Co-drivers: Are there factors that **INFLUENCE** the resilience of what to what but are hardly manipulable?

Co-drivers are factors that mediate the response of the social-ecological system to disturbances or stressors but, conversely to resilience predictors, they cannot be manipulated to increase resilience. See [D1.1](#) (Hurtado et al. 2022) for a literature review of the co-drivers reported in studies of resilience in forest social-ecological systems. Note that literature often does not distinguish predictors based on the ability to manage/manipulate them (Albrich et al. 2020). Predictors that cannot be managed in a meaningful manner are referred to as co-drivers, which are susceptible to be managed or not. Notably, co-drivers often interact with resilience predictors, thus modulating the predictor's role and providing context, in which the effect of resilience predictors is more or less significant.

Co-drivers often correspond to physical characteristics (e.g., soils, topography) and climatic parameters, which have a geographical basis, as well as socio-political contexts (e.g., national regulations) and legacies or path dependence (Moen and Keskitalo 2010; Johnstone et al. 2016). They are usually sensitive to the spatio-temporal scale, and at some level, can become resilience predictors if they become manipulable. Strictly, past memory, legacy, and path dependence cannot be managed and should be considered as co-drivers, although they can inform about management actions promoting resilience. Climate change should also be considered as a co-driver, particularly at short-term local scales, since the effects of climate change mitigation are far from being operative at these scales; however, mitigation actions could be considered as predictors when assessments of resilience at a large or global scale are based on projected scenarios. Disturbance regimes often perform as co-drivers, particularly when assessing resilience in face of an existing disturbance regime that cannot be modified (e.g., drought occurrence). When the disturbance regime can be manipulated as a management action to promote resilience, it would act as a resilience predictor. For example, the intensity of wildfires a priori determines the resilience of the vegetation cover and therefore performs as "co-driver", but the number, frequency, and extent of prescribed fires used to reduce fuel and promote resilience at the landscape scale, perform as predictors of resilience. Similarly, the general regulations that influence the forest value chain, or the degree of market integration of forest-based products, often act as co-drivers since they cannot be easily modified locally; but at a broader regional or national level, regulations can be changed to improve the resilience of certain variables of the value chain, thus becoming predictors.

2.3 Application of the ORF concepts

The application of the ORF in each case should be based on the identification of the ORF's different elements, and their logical connection. Eventually, the main aim of the ORF is to provide a standardized and straightforward procedure to identify variables that are susceptible to being managed to promote the maintenance of ecosystem services or certain levels of the components of the forest value chain. ORF follows a deterministic approach, which enables the establishment of an operational procedure that allows resilience to be quantified and compared over time and between different situations. This approach corresponds to a specific resilience (*sensu* Folke et al. 2010) and has the problem that the resilience of some parts of the system does not ensure the resilience of others or the whole system. However, an analysis

of the overall resilience of the system - closer to general resilience (*sensu* Folke et al. 2010) - may be attained by the ORF approximation if variables that describe the system as a whole are used.

The application of the ORF is case-specific and therefore exhibits great flexibility. In each situation, its different elements must be identified, answering the following questions: (1) what system variables are relevant? (2) what disturbance or stressor is operating and at what spatio-temporal scale? (3) what is the reference state? (4) what is the most appropriate metric to measure resilience? (5) what are the potential predictors and co-drivers? Note that a certain variable can play different roles in different cases; a system variable in a given case can perform as a predictor in another case. For example, tree diversity can be a predictor of the resilience of forest primary production, but we can also assess the resilience of diversity and, in that case, it acts as a system variable. In addition, a variable may behave as a predictor or co-driver depending on whether it is the object of manipulation in that specific case. Likewise, this flexibility in the role of specific variables within the ORF is particularly manifested when different scales are considered. For example, forest management practices may be powerful predictors of resilience at the plot level, but the general management model applied in the territory can also act as a co-driver for certain system variables (e.g., forest area) which are assessed at wide spatial and temporal scales. On the other hand, some intensive management actions can act as disturbances to which variables, such as those associated with biodiversity, respond with more or less resilience. Even though the ORF application has an important ad-hoc component, it allows for establishing a common framework for resilience assessments carried out in very different contexts. To better understand the main concepts that comprise the operational resilience framework, we provide hypothetical examples in Box 1 about the identification of these concepts and their narrative link.

Box 1: Application of the ORF in a hypothetical study case, by highlighting in the text its different elements.

Example 1

In this study we aim to assess the effect of **catastrophic windthrow**⁽⁴⁾ on **harvested round wood timber volume and unit price**⁽²⁾ of the social-ecological system of **the National Forest Estate**⁽¹⁾ at **regional scale**⁽⁵⁾. To that end, we use **return time to pre-disturbance state**⁽⁶⁾ to quantify changes of **harvested round wood volume and unit price**⁽²⁾ in comparison to **pre-disturbance level**⁽³⁾. We assess the role of **management systems and disturbance intensity**⁽⁸⁾ mediating this response, and we expect **forest landscape heterogeneity and public-private ability to coordinate for quick harvesting deployment**⁽⁷⁾ as predictors of resilience.

Example 2

In this study we aim to assess the effect of **drought**⁽⁴⁾ on **radial growth responses**⁽²⁾ of **Mediterranean tree species**⁽¹⁾ at **plot scale**⁽⁵⁾. To that end, we use **resistance, recovery and resilience indices**⁽⁶⁾ to quantify changes on **basal area increment**⁽²⁾ in comparison to **pre-disturbance conditions**⁽³⁾. To calculate the indices we define a period of **three years before and after** the disturbance⁽⁵⁾. We assess the role of **drought intensity and species distribution range**⁽⁸⁾ mediating this response, and we expect the **mean tree age**⁽⁷⁾ as predictor of resilience.

- (1) **Case study of social-economical system**
- (2) **System variables** (OF)
- (3) **Reference state** (COMPARED TO)
- (4) **Disturbance or stressor** (TO)
- (5) **Spatio-temporal scale** (WHEN and WHERE)
- (6) **Metric** (HOW)
- (7) **Resilience Predictor** (MODIFIED/MANAGED)
- (8) **Co-driver** (INFLUENCE)

The roadmap for applying ORF concepts to resilience assessment in specific cases includes seven steps (see Fig. 2):

1. Selection and quantification of system variables, with a particular focus on those describing ecosystem services and related value chains of the forest social-ecological system.
2. Identification and description of potential disturbance regimes and stressors, in the face of which resilience will be assessed; their characteristics usually have a strong influence on resilience.
3. Identification and quantification of the reference state, which may correspond to undisturbed systems or desired alternative states, especially when addressing forest social-ecological systems. For such purpose, explicit recognition of the temporal (days, years, decades) and the spatial (e.g., in forests, tree, stand, landscape, region, country) scales at which resilience is assessed is needed. Spatial scales are also often well related to the levels of organization and levels of decision-making.
4. Measurement of resilience by applying a convenient metric, according to the spatio-temporal scale, the number and characteristics of the system variables, and available information. Importantly, this measurement corresponds to the comparison of the observed variables to the reference state.
5. Selection of potential resilience predictors and co-drivers, and assessment of their effects following analytical procedures coming from empirical or experimental observations together with statistical models, mechanistic models, or surveys from stakeholders' expertise. Based on statistical inference, resilience predictors and co-drivers will inform on the resilience of relevant system variables of the forest social-ecological system and they would commonly correspond to environmental or social gradients, or to different scenarios (e.g., climate, management, legacy). The distinction between predictors and co-drivers will follow the criterion of their potential to be manipulated and used in management actions, and depend on the scale considered and the specific social and ecological contexts.
6. Prioritization of key resilience predictors, or combination of sets of them which determine multiple or single system variables. For instance, a single resilience predictor may inform about the resilience of several system variables, which may be more or less correlated between them, or several predictors may have a similar role on the resilience of given system variables, or the resilience of a system variable can be only explained by a set of specific predictors. A similar network of relationships applies to co-drivers and system variables. Procedures based on multivariate, structural equation models and causal analysis, or network analyses may be useful to disentangle the links between resilience predictors or co-drivers and system variables. However, mechanistic explanations of these links are essential in this step to avoid spurious relationships and to support the extrapolation of the use of predictors in other situations.
7. Integrative assessments of resilience require considering trade-offs and synergies between system variables, which would usually correspond to forest ecosystem services and elements of the forest value chain (Nikinmaa et al. 2023). These trade-offs translate to resilience predictors, whose weight and threshold values should be integrated in algorithms or rationales developed for this assessment. The contribution of actors, such as decision-makers and stakeholders, is essential to establish these trade-offs and synergies, as well as to evaluate the utility of resilience predictors to implement management actions under contexts determined by co-drivers. Also, quantitative procedures based on multicriteria analysis and optimization modeling are particularly useful for this purpose.

Figure 2. Steps for applying the ORF concepts to the resilience assessment in specific cases.

3 Framing other resilience-related concepts in the ORF

3.1 Resistance and recovery

When experiencing a disturbance, the system variables are altered and, later, recover to a greater or lesser degree, determining its resilience (engineering resilience), also called elasticity. These two phases - the immediate impact of the disturbance and the subsequent recuperation - have often been explicitly recognized in studies on engineering resilience (Hodgson et al 2015), and received different names. Common denominations recognize "resistance" as the first phase, in which the disturbance alters the system, changing its variables (Grimm and Wiesel 1997; Standish et al. 2014; Van Meerbeek et al 2021); so, the inverse of resistance would correspond to "severity", a term that indicates the impact of disturbance (Pickett and White 1985). In a following stage, "recovery" corresponds to the phase in which the system recovers its properties. Finally, "resilience" refers to the situation of the state with respect to the status prior to the disturbance (e.g., Lloret et al. 2011, Ingrisich and Bahn 2018; de Bello et al 2021), or to the absence of disturbances. Nevertheless, some frameworks use the term "resilience" for the recovery phase as the time to return to a reference state (Isbell et al. 2015) and "recovery" for the final state of full return (Donohue et al. 2016; Hildebrand et al. 2018; Van Meerbeek et al 2021). The use of measures that relate these phases, either through indices that weight recovery as a function of resistance (e.g., relative resilience, Lloret et al 2011) or through the deviation from the inverse relationship between recovery and resistance (Ingrisich and Bahn 2018) have been proposed to describe the overall process.

Nevertheless, the differentiated measure of resistance and recovery is particularly supported by the fact that the involved mechanisms are not necessarily the same (e.g., Blanco-Rodríguez and Espelta 2022). For example, in the event of a forest wildfire, resistance is

particularly determined by the quantity and distribution of the fuel, while recovery is determined by the characteristics of the soil and by the availability of protected buds and seed banks (Lecina et al. 2021). However, these phases are not entirely independent (Zheng et al. 2021), since the lower the resistance, the greater room for recovery to the pre-disturbance situation, and vice versa. Therefore, a comprehensive assessment of resilience includes the combination of these phases, which should be analysed separately with different metrics based on the relationships of the system variables between different moments in the time sequence (e.g., Lloret et al 2011; Zehng et al. 2021), including the time elapsed until the system fully recovers (Standish et al. 2014; Thum et al. 2016). For example, prolonged disturbance impacts may remain, and damage may also appear afterward, delayed in time. In turn, resistance operates during or shortly after the disturbance, resulting in a certain convergence between the measures of resistance and short-term resilience, particularly when the moment of the disturbance is prolonged in time or is not well defined (e.g., long periods of drought, or lasting diseases and pest infestations). On the other hand, the stability measures that correspond to an approximation of ecological resilience and that indicate the maintenance in a certain state subject to fluctuations or slight disturbances can also be associated with the concept of resistance; thus, a high resistance would be a sign of stability (see below).

The existence of different phases in the process of resilience associated with disturbances fits well into the ORF. First, the reference state is a priori well established as the situation before the disturbance. However, undisturbed or "normal" situations can be preferred as a reference state (e.g., Isbell et al. 2015) since, in historical systems, the previous conditions are not repeated and disturbed and undisturbed areas are evolving simultaneously. Second, the disturbances, or their regime, that trigger and largely determine resistance and subsequent recovery, are explicitly recognized in the ORF. Finally, resistance and recovery can be considered as two metrics used to estimate different components of resilience, closely dependent on the time scale and the period considered. Therefore, the predictors and co-drivers of these phases or components of resilience can be different, reflecting the flexibility of the ORF application.

3.2 Stability

The concept of stability is subject to multiple interpretations and uses (Grimm and Wissel 1997; Donohue et al. 2016; Kéfi et al. 2019). It has been considered a "*multidimensional concept that tries to capture the different aspects of the dynamics of the system and its response to perturbations*" (Donohue et al. 2016), and therefore is closely linked to resilience. In a general way, stability corresponds to the maintenance of the properties of the system within certain margins, thus describing its variability, acknowledging that the system presents fluctuations controlled by regulatory feedbacks that maintain it within these margins. Stability, therefore, contemplates several components or dimensions, which are not independent of each other, such as persistence - maintenance over time of a certain state -, variability through time - which corresponds to the inverse of constancy -, resistance, and recovery - also called resilience (Donohue et al 2016; Hillebrand et al. 2018; de Bello et al 2021). These components are reflected in turn in the concepts of ecological and engineering resilience. Thus, persistence, which is intrinsically associated with a certain variability of system variables, implicitly refers to the existence of tipping points that lead to alternative states and determine the loss of ecological resilience. On the other hand, this stability associated with persistence is interrupted by disturbances that can bring the system close to the thresholds that lead to a state change; alternatively, the system may be able to minimize the changes induced by the disturbance or recover afterward (engineering resilience).

Numerous proposals have been made to measure stability based on its multidimensional nature (Grimm and Wissel 1997; Van Meerbeek et al. 2021; de Bello et al. 2021; Donohue et al. 2016). At an operational level, and in the absence of disturbances, one of its most evident dimensions can be easily estimated from the inverse of the temporal variability of the system variables (e.g., de Bello et al 2021), although this measure, by itself, does not refer to a change of state and therefore to ecological resilience. On the other hand, the empirical measurement of resilience as the ability to remain, without reaching the threshold that leads to a change of state, encounters the operational difficulty that it can only be done when the system has already reached this threshold. The alternative is looking for estimators or early warning signals, which indicate that the system is presumably close to a tipping point (Dakos et al. 2014).

An important element enhanced by the ORF is the role of stressors that affect the system (e.g., climate change), and that can eventually lead to thresholds of alternative systems (Kéfi et al. 2019). These stressors may not be explicit in stability analyses, particularly when dealing with permanence and variability. In addition, the distinction between stressors and disturbances may not always be clear (Van Meerbeek et al. 2021) when strictly applying a stability perspective. However, when considering the stability from the perspective of resilience, we must make them explicit, and estimate them; this would allow to distinguish the intrinsic variability of the system from the one induced by these stressors and disturbances. On the other hand, applying the concept of resilience in a stability analysis context requires the use of a broad time scale to capture trends superimposed on the variability inherent to the system, i.e., in the absence of stressors or disturbances.

In summary, resilience and stability are closely linked concepts, and they often converge. Nevertheless, they usually focus on somewhat different aspects. For example, disturbances or stress may not be essential in the analysis of stability, while a resilience analysis is usually performed as a response to a specific disturbance or stressor. Overall, the ORF integrates the dimensions of stability with the resilience of the system from an operational perspective through (1) a procedure based on the definition of a reference state that corresponds to a certain range of values of the system variables, (2) the explicit search for the mechanisms that promote resilience, reflected in the predictors and co-drivers of resilience, (3) identifying and referring the system dynamics to certain spatial and temporal scales and to disturbances or stressors that operate on them and that challenge the maintenance of the system variables, (4) using adequate resilience metrics, such as variability measures or early warning signals in the case of ecological resilience.

3.3 Vulnerability

Like resilience, vulnerability has acquired multiple meanings, and among the attempts to systematize it, the IPCC definition has become a reference by considering it “*the propensity or predisposition of exposed elements to be adversely affected when impacted by hazard events, including sensitivity or susceptibility to harm and related to a lack of capacity to adapt*” (Cardona et al. 2012; IPCC 2018). Vulnerability is a component of risk, and it is directly associated with sensitivity to the exposure to hazard - which in turn includes both the probability of an adverse phenomenon to occur and its magnitude - and to further adaptation capacity. The concordance between the vulnerability and resilience approaches has been previously explored (Manyena 2006; Milller et al 2010), and an overall inverse relationship between the two concepts can be recognized - since little resilience implies more vulnerability (Milller et al 2010), and vice versa. Indeed, both the resilience and vulnerability conceptual frameworks address the system's reaction to disturbances or stressors, so they share some essential elements. Exposure to a hazard within the risk/vulnerability framework often

corresponds to descriptors of disturbance regimes (frequency, magnitude, extent) or to more gradual environmental change, as recognized within the resilience framework. In turn, sensitivity or susceptibility within the vulnerability framework is explained by mechanisms, such as regulatory feedbacks, that also explain resilience. Finally, adaptation capacity can play a role in the recovery after disturbances and is a key component of social-ecological resilience, in which policy, management, and social responses adjusting the system functioning play a major role (Folke et al. 2010). Reciprocally, the different elements of the ORF can also be recognized in the framework of vulnerability, particularly if we intend to carry out an operational analysis. For instance, similarly to resilience, vulnerability refers to certain system variables, whose response to disturbances or stressors is expected to be determined by certain drivers, all of them operating at a certain spatio-temporal scale.

Nevertheless, conceptual differences between the vulnerability and the resilience frameworks should also be considered (Manyena 2006). Some distinctions appear in the weight that the resilience and vulnerability approaches give to the components of the ORF. Vulnerability is embedded in the more general framework of risk framework, which explicitly considers the role of exposure and hazard magnitude, thus, defining risk as the product of exposure, hazard magnitude, and vulnerability. In the resilience framework, the disturbance regime is recognized, but it is considered as an external agent and often it is not so intensively analysed and integrated with resilience responses (but see Johnstone et al 2016), probably because of the difficulties to obtain empirical information on the system's response. In turn, the reference state and the measures that compare it with the observed system are usually not as explicit in vulnerability analysis as they are in the resilience one, particularly when addressing disturbances in the engineering resilience approach. This is probably because vulnerability analysis is more focused on actors suffering or reversing vulnerability than on the mechanistic functioning of the system (Miller et al 2010). Therefore, the mechanisms that promote resilience, and the predictors that describe them, are usually well addressed and measured in resilience studies, while they many times are only implicit in vulnerability analyses, which often just provide general assessments based on theoretical principles. Finally, vulnerability considers the capacity of adaptation to a new environment as a fundamental part, when referring to processes of adjustment to given conditions, such as climate change. In the case of resilience, while adaptation capacity is well recognized in the social subsystem, for instance as the capacity to restructure their components to maintain their functionality, the adaptation concept in the forest ecosystem subsystem may be subjected to different meanings. While adjustment is implicit in the absence of disturbances within the ecosystem resilience approach, it may not be completely equivalent to post-disturbance recovery, since this recovery can occur thanks to pre-existing legacies that do not properly require selective adaptation to the new situation (Johnson et al. 2016).

In short, vulnerability and resilience can be included in a common scheme, since they analyse the same phenomenon and roughly have an inverse relationship. The recognition of resilience and vulnerability in a common framework allows the interpretation of these differences and the identification of common, robust patterns. However, their perspectives are not identical and they give distinct weights to the components of their respective frameworks, providing complementary views.

4 Concluding remarks and further prospects

What makes the Operational Resilience Framework (ORF) presented here particularly distinctive in contrast with other resilience approaches is its operational vocation in the sense of providing a contrasted tool to find predictors of resilience that can be the object of decision-making and management, encompassing both ecological and social-economical perspectives.

Additionally, the ORF elements allow encompassing resilience assessments done in different situations under a common frame. ORF elements are commonly used in the literature ([D1.1](#), Hurtado et al. 2022, and [D1.2](#), Jaime et al. 2023), even though a shared narrative of resilience assessment is lacking overall. So, we encourage the explicit recognition of ORF elements in further studies. This would bring standardization that, in turn, will lead to sound comparisons and consequently to better-supported recommendations aimed at improving resilience in social-ecological systems.

A major challenge for sound assessments of resilience is quantification, which is particularly poor in the evaluation of resilience from a social-economical perspective. ORF can embrace qualitative analyses based on categorical parameters and is very flexible in the use of distinct metrics, scales, disturbances, or stressors, particularly on the establishment of the reference state, which can be adapted to specific cases. ORF recognizes resilience as a relative phenomenon in terms of its elements. This means that the resilience predictors and co-drivers can vary depending on the decisions made when defining those elements of the ORF. That is, the ORF procedure, by following an operational orientation according to the "what to what" scheme, is mainly aimed at making assessments of specific resilience (*sensu* Folke et al. 2010). An analysis of general resilience (*sensu* Folke et al. 2010) in social-ecological systems usually follows an agent-based approach (Miller et al. 2010), to the detriment of the operability of the analysis and its application. However, the narrative proposed by ORF can complement this approach, and contribute to find descriptors of the whole system suitable to be compared to desired situations - corresponding to ORF reference state - and further predictors of the appropriate behaviour of the system.

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